

LINEAR AND NONLINEAR ELASTIC PROPERTIES OF POLYSTYRENE-BASED NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Polystyrene-based composites filled with particles of different type and shape have been fabricated by melt technology. Linear and nonlinear elastic properties of composite samples with different concentrations of fillers were studied. The most considerable increase of elastic modulus was demonstrated with introduction of carbon black and multi-walled carbon nanotubes. The behaviour of nonlinear strain waves in composites was studied and noticeable decrease of attenuation coefficient was demonstrated. The ultrasound-based methodology for measurement of nonlinear elastic moduli was evaluated.

1 INTRODUCTION

Micro- and nanostructured composites become increasingly popular nowadays in various engineering applications. Most of them contain ordered inclusions, i.e., they are manufactured in the form of a matrix filled with oriented filaments made of another material. Disordered composites are of common interest as well, with most intriguing ones being filled with nanoparticles, which can drastically improve the resulting material strength, stiffness and other physical parameters. Several examples were published recently demonstrating advantages of nanocomposites [1-3], in particular in view of their potential multifunctionality.

Polymer composites are finding increasingly wide applications in aerospace, marine and automotive industries, where components experience various dynamic loads. Rapidly growing applications of composite materials in industry stimulate analysis of various aspects of their mechanical behavior. However the composite response to intense dynamic loading is often hard to predict since it may depend drastically not only upon matrix and filler characteristics, but also on filler distribution in the matrix and on resulting mechanical characteristics of the composite, including its nonlinear parameters, third-order elastic moduli in particular. Glassy polymers are known to exhibit nonlinear elastic properties. Nanocomposites fabricated on the base of these polymers can be expected to demonstrate nonlinear elasticity as well.

Wave processes in general are good candidates for modeling dynamic loading of materials. Nonlinear elastic strain waves and in particular bulk strain solitary waves (solitons) may be most promising due to their anomalously low decay, stability of wave parameters in homogeneous waveguides and dependence of parameters on waveguide elasticity and geometry. Besides that these waves can be applied for measuring third order elastic moduli of materials which are currently measured with low accuracy.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Composite samples were fabricated from the polystyrene matrix being filled with different inclusions: silicon dioxide particles Aerosil R812 modified by silazane, Alumina nanoparticles (Al_2O_3) Aeroxide Alu C805 modified by octylsilane, Carbon Black (CB) P-805E, Multi-walled carbon nanotubes (CNT) CTube-100, Halloysite Natural Tubules (HNT), Sheet silicate (phyllosilicate) minerals Mica ME-100, and Montmorillonite 15A (MMT). The concentration of nanoparticles, measured with regard to polymer weight, amounted to $K = 0, 5, 10,$ and 20 wt%. Block samples of composites were obtained by melt technology.

2.2 Experimental methodologies

The filler influence on thermomechanical properties of the composites was studied using dynamic mechanical analysis. The dispersion of nanoparticles in the polymer matrix was evaluated from micrographs of the cryo-fracture surface of the composite samples, taken by a scanning electron microscope. An influence of particles concentration on mechanical properties was tested using Instron system. The mechanical properties were studied in uniaxial tension and three-point bending tests. Basing on the data obtained, the strength at break, strain at break and elastic modulus of composites were determined. The nonlinear elastic moduli were determined from ultrasonic measurements. Generation and evolution of strain solitons in composites were studied using digital holographic recording of waves propagating in compound waveguides (see [4,5] for details of experimental procedure).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Melt viscosity and filler distribution

The introduction of all particles resulted in an increase of melt viscosity in proportion to filler concentration, with the exception of composites with Mica. The most pronounced effect was observed for composites with MMT, CNT and Al_2O_3 . The effective viscosity of the polymer at filler concentrations used increased by an average of 2 to 5 orders of magnitude over pure PS. We believe that this increase is indicative of the formation of a network structure between the polymer and filler particles. At low concentrations all the fillers were rather uniformly distributed in the PS matrix. At higher concentrations, agglomerates with the size of few μm were observed. Examples are shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Filler distribution in the PS matrix: (a) 3% MMT, (b) 10% Al_2O_3 , (c) 10% CNT.

3.2 Elastic properties

The data obtained on mechanical properties of PS-based composites filled with different types of particles are summarized in Table 1. It was shown that the introduction of up to 5% of Mica can

increase the stiffness of composites and maintain their strength at the level of pure PS without considerable embrittlement of samples. The introduction of HNT and MMT led to an increase in composite stiffness but reduced the strength and elasticity of the material. A significant increase in the flexural elastic modulus (up to 50%) was reached upon addition of 10% HNTs or 5% Mica. In general the introduction of more rigid particles led to an increase in the elastic modulus of composites. The most pronounced rise was observed with carbon nanoparticles. The elastic modulus increased from 1.6 GPa for pure PS to 2.8 GPa for composites filled with 10wt% of CNT or CB. The data on elastic modulus of composites as function of filler concentration is plotted in Fig. 2.

Sample	Strength at break (MPa)	Elastic modulus, (GPa)	Strain at break, %
<i>PS</i>	56±1	1.6±0.1	5.6±0.2
<i>PS+3% Mica</i>	54±2	1.86±0.04	4.1±0.21
<i>PS+5% Mica</i>	56±5	1.94±0.05	3.9±0.3
<i>PS+5% HNT</i>	52±1	1.68±0.15	5.7±0.3
<i>PS+10% HNT</i>	49±6	2.0±0.06	2.8±0.5
<i>PS+3% MMT</i>	50±4	1.89±0.04	2.9±0.3
<i>PS+5% MMT</i>	46±2	1.93±0.07	2.6±0.2
<i>PS+5% SiO₂</i>	52±2	1.68±0.15	5.7±0.3
<i>PS+20% SiO₂</i>	31±3	1.83±0.2	2.2±0.2
<i>PS+10% Al₂O₃</i>	57±1	1.9±0.1	4.1±0.5
<i>PS+20% Al₂O₃</i>	49±1	2.0±0.1	3.1±0.2
<i>PS+10% CB</i>	74±2	2.8±0.1	2.4±0.3
<i>PS+20% CB</i>	65±5	3.0±0.2	2.1±0.6
<i>PS+5% CNT</i>	53±3	2.6±0.2	1.9±0.3
<i>PS+10% CNT</i>	49±3	2.8±0.2	1.7±0.2

Table 1: Mechanical properties of PS-based composites with different fillings.

Figure 3: Elastic modulus of PS-based composites as function of filler concentration.

3.3 Nonlinear elastic properties

The nonlinear elastic behavior of fabricated nanocomposite samples was evaluated based on the analysis of generation and evolution of nonlinear strain waves (solitons) in them. Experiments were performed in 3-layer laminates containing a middle layer of commercial transparent PS (pure PS) and 2 outer layers made of either PS used as a matrix or the manufactured composite. The waveguide schematics are shown in Fig. 3 a,c. Layers were bonded by the ethylcyanoacrylate adhesive which provides almost perfect contact between adherends made of glassy polymers [5]. It was previously shown that in such a compound waveguide a single soliton is formed with parameters depending upon soliton parameters in homogeneous waveguides of the same geometry made of adherend materials. Soliton amplitude, shape and velocity in the opaque composite layer can be estimated from corresponding parameters of the wave in the transparent layer of pure PS being recorded by means of digital holography and with regard of elastic moduli of both materials (see [6] for details). The data on linear elastic parameters of both contacting materials, nonlinear elastic moduli of pure polymer and measured soliton parameters in the laminated waveguide are sufficient to obtain information on the nonlinearity coefficient β of the composite. This coefficient, comprising a combination of the second- (E, ν) and third- (l, m, n) order elastic moduli of the material, governs its nonlinear elastic properties [7]:

$$\beta \equiv 3E + 2l(1 - 2\nu)^3 + 4m(1 + \nu)^2(1 - 2\nu) + 6n\nu^2 \quad (1)$$

Figure 4: Strain solitons in 3-layered laminated bars. (a,c) – waveguide schematics: *PS pure* is commercial transparent polystyrene, *PS* is polystyrene used as a matrix and fabricated by the same technology as a composite, *Composite* is PS+10% HNT composite. (b,d) – phase shift distributions recorded in designated areas of the waveguide corresponding to strain solitons.

Solitons were monitored during their propagation along the waveguides, and changes in their amplitude, shape and velocity were analyzed. Examples of soliton evolution in the waveguides with layers made of PS and PS+10%HNT are shown in Fig. 3b,d. The comparison clearly demonstrates a noticeable difference in soliton attenuation, which is much lower in the composite-containing

waveguide. The obtained values of decay decrement comprise $\alpha_{\text{PS}} = 0.041 \pm 0.006 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\alpha_{\text{comp}} = 0.018 \pm 0.004 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The soliton velocity in composite-containing waveguide was measured to be 1790 m/s that is slightly higher than that in pure PS (1772 m/s). These observations demonstrate considerable effect of composite elasticity onto soliton parameters that cannot be described acceptably by a change in Young's modulus. The correct description requires data on nonlinear elastic moduli and coefficient β (eq. 1) of the composite.

Obviously the third-order moduli of composites depend drastically not only on the type and concentration of inclusions but also on their distribution in the matrix. Inhomogeneous distribution and formation of agglomerates can cause considerable changes in these parameters. That means that measurements of these parameters are to be made for each composite sample. As shown in [8] the analysis of the dependence of ultrasound velocity in the sample upon the applied stress can provide data for determination of nonlinear elastic moduli of the material. We tested this approach on samples of pure PS. Figure 5 presents the effective P-wave modulus (M) as function of applied transverse pressure (T). The theoretical analysis performed showed that at low pressures M depends linearly on T : $M = M_0 + \gamma T$, where $M_0 = \lambda + 2\mu$, and the dimensionless slope coefficient γ is a function of the third-order (Murnaghan) elastic moduli:

$$\gamma = -\frac{1}{3\lambda + 2\mu} \left[2l - \frac{\lambda}{\mu} (2m + \lambda + 2\mu) \right] \quad (2)$$

where λ and μ are second-order Lamé moduli. Since Poisson coefficient for most polymers equals to 0.3, we assume $\lambda = 2\mu$, and then the nonlinear modulus $l-2m$ can be written in a form:

$$l - 2m = (1 - \gamma)M_0 \quad (3)$$

Using measurement data in Fig. 5 we obtain for PS: $M_0 = 5.71 \text{ GPa}$, $\gamma = 1.51 \pm 0.03$, and $l-2m = -2.80 \pm 0.03 \text{ GPa}$. This value corresponds relatively well with that calculated from measurements by Hughes and Kelly ([9]): $l-2m = -7.7 \pm 0.3 \text{ GPa}$. Note that their data, obtained as long ago as in 1953, are the only available experimental data on third-order elastic moduli for PS. To measure all the three Murnaghan moduli a similar experiment should be performed with transverse ultrasound waves.

Figure 5: Effective P-wave modulus (M) as function of applied transverse pressure (T) for pure PS.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The results obtained and suggested methodologies can be of use for estimation of both linear and nonlinear elastic properties of composite materials. Strain solitons can be applied for evaluation of operational stability of functional and structural components made of reinforced polymeric composites. On the other hand the possibility of strain soliton generation in different structures, especially in those used in important branches of industry, such as aerospace engineering and oil and gas transportation, should be taken into consideration.

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